

LAND USE LAND COVER MAPPING FOR JINTUR WATERSHED BY USING REMOTE SENSING AND GIS

S. D. Payal 1.S.B. Jadhav 2. V. K. Ingle 3

1- Associate Professor, Dept. of Soil and Water Conservation Engineering, CAET, VNMKV, Parbhani

2- Professor Dept of Irrigation and Drainage Engineering, CAET, VNMKV, Parbhani

3- Assistant Professor Dept of Irrigation and Drainage Engineering, CAET, VNMKV, Parbhani

sandippayal35@gmail.com

MS Received: 05.08.2024; MS Revised: 30.04.2024; MS Accepted: 01.09.2024

MS 3247 (RESEARCH PAPER IN SOIL AND WATER CONSERVATION ENGINEERING,)

Abstract

The study titled land use/land cover mapping for Jintur watershed using remote sensing and geographical information system (GIS) technique was conducted in the Parbhani district of Maharashtra during the 2022-23 period. In this research, the application of remote sensing and geographical information system (GIS) technology was employed to delineate the watershed boundary, create thematic maps, classify land use/land cover, and determine suitable locations for soil and water conservation measures. ArcGIS 10.7 software facilitated these processes. The Jintur watershed is having total area of 909.05 square kilometers in the Marathwada region of Maharashtra. For the land use/land cover classification, satellite imagery was employed, and supervised classification method was applied within ArcGIS 10.7 software. Five distinct classes were identified: the level one land uses classes are agriculture, water body, forest, settlement, and wasteland along with major drainage and roads.

It can be seen from the table 1 that maximum area is under the agricultural land i.e. 503.15 sq.km (55.43 percent) of the watershed followed by wasteland 350.40 sq.km (38.60 per-cent) out of total watershed area water bodies cover 11.95 sq.km (1.32 per-cent), forest covers 38.78 sq.km (4.27 per-cent) and settlement covers 3.45 sq.km (0.38 per-cent).

Keyword: Mapping, Watershed, Remote Sensing

Introduction

Watershed is the area which contributes runoff water to a common point. The term watershed is crucial in the context of soil and water conservation. It refers to an area of land where water flows across the surface and eventually gathers in the same body of water, such as a stream, river, lake, or the sea. The water follows the highest elevation along channels and converges at the lowest point, where it continues its flow along the water course and eventually reaches the mouth of waterways. Remote sensing is the science and art of obtaining information about an object, area, or phenomenon by analysing data obtained by a device that is not in contact with the object, area, or event under inquiry is known as remote sensing. A Geographic Information System (GIS) is a computer-based tool used to organize, analyse, and display geographical data and spatial relationships. It integrates traditional database functionality with mapping capabilities, allowing for the visualization and analysis of various types of data, such as demographic information, economic development opportunities, and plant species distribution. Land use/land cover knowledge is an important for many planning and management events and it is considered as necessary component for modelling and understanding the earth as system (G. reenivasulu, 2014). Land use/land cover (LULC) is defined as the biophysical condition/characteristics of the earth's surface. Remote sensing and Geographical Information Systems (GIS) are powerful tools to derive accurate and timely information on the spatial distribution of land use/land cover changes over large areas. Past and present studies conducted by organizations and institutions around the world, mostly has concentrated on the application of LULC changes. The visual interpretation of the IRS data led to the identification and delineation of land use/land cover categories such as agriculture, wasteland, impervious surface, forest, pasture, shrub and snow. The term of land cover relates to the type of object present on the earth surface. Agricultural fields, Waterbodies, Forested areas, and Orchards are related to the land cover and Buildings, structures, highways or any other constructions are the type of the land use. Thereby the term of land use land cover is very important for understanding the land utilization pattern. Materials and Methods Study Area The study area is selected for the research is Jintur watershed from Godavari Purna basin most of the watershed situated in Parbhani district.

Land Use and Land Cover Database

Data was downloaded from the USGS web site. The raw Landsat-8 data with band combination band number 3 (Green: 0.53-0.59 μm), 4 (Red: 0.64 – 0.67 μm) and 5 (NIR: 0.85 – 0.88) with 30 m resolution were selected to produce FCC (False color composite) image. The same database was rectified with topo maps to get drainage and

satellite images with common location properties. To perform the supervised classification ground truth data was used to demarc training site in Erdas Imagine software. A level-1 land use class includes agriculture, forest, water body, and wasteland and settlement classes. The Landsat-8 image was of 30 m ground resolution, so that only a major settlement was demarked using hybrid approach of classification. The major area was classified using digital image process and desired correction in final layer was performed using ground realities and on-screen digitization techniques. Final statistics was compiled in excel, the forest boundary was derived from topo maps and same used in land use classification. Presently, forest area was appeared as degraded for on satellite image. The level one land uses classes are Agriculture, Water body, Forest, Settlement, and Wasteland along with major drainage and roads. In this method satellite data is download and data rectification is done for classification of land use classes and finally results are recorded. The flow process is shown as follows and in Fig 1.

Data was used for data on, compilation and calculating morphometric parameters. The assign projection system was Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) WGS (1984) datum and spheroid System. ArcGIS 10.7 software was used to extract the drainage network and watershed boundary from the digital elevation model.

Data Pre-processing

The image pre-processing step is crucial in the context of land use/land cover mapping. It involves the elimination of undesirable distortions and inaccuracies found in satellite images, rectifying geometric errors, filtering the imagery, improving overall image quality, and boosting pixel brightness. This preparatory phase is essential for ensuring accurate and reliable results in land use/land cover mapping processes.

Land Use and Land Cover Classification

In ArcGIS 10.7 Software, there are typically two methods for image classifications: Unsupervised classification and supervised classification. For this specific research, the supervised classification method was employed to identify training samples. In the supervised classification process, a few training samples are collected for each class of interest. These training samples are areas or pixels in the image that are known to belong to a specific land cover or land use category. The collected training samples are then merged using the aqua; Merge tool " in ArcGIS 10.7. During this step, suitable class names are assigned to each training sample, and appropriate colours can be used to represent the classes. Identification of training samples the training set is established using a supervised classification approach. In this process, specific training samples are identified and labelled to represent distinct land cover or land use categories. These samples serve as representative areas or pixels with known characteristics,

which are used to train the classification algorithm to accurately classify the rest of the image based on their spectral properties

.Results

Data rectification Fig 1

Results and Discussion

Classification method for land use land cover:

Classifying the satellite images to extract the Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) theme is one of the major steps in this study. Classification is the process of assigning classes to the pixels in images. Moreover, successful utilization of remotely sensed data for LULC studies demands careful selection of an appropriate data set and image processing techniques (Lunetta, 1998). The most common image analysis for extracting LULC is digital image classification. Sabins (1997) explains that image classification techniques are most generally applied to the spectral data of a single-date image or to the varying spectral data of a series of multi-data images. The complexity of image classification techniques can range from the use of a simple threshold value for a single spectral band to complex statistically based decision rules that operate on multivariate data. The purpose of image classification is to label the pixels in the image with the real information (Jensen & Gorte, 2001). (Mather, 2001). Classification involves labelling the pixels as belonging to particular classes using the spectral data available. There are two broad types of classification procedure and each finds application in processing of Remote sensing image. One is referred to as supervised classification and the other one is unsupervised.. These can be used as alternative approaches but are often combined into hybrid methodologies using more than one method (Richards and Jia, 2006). Both the supervised and unsupervised classification methods used for classifying various multispectral images which are based on so called traditional pixel based method which has been played a great importance for classifying low resolution images.

Land use land cover:

The land use land cover map of the study area has been prepared through the remotely sensed data obtained from IRS-P6 sensors LISS-III for 2014 and Table 1 present the false colour composite (FCC) of band infra-red, red and green (band 3, 2 and 1) assigned red, green and blue colour respectively. The land use/land cover classes identified in the watershed are forest, wasteland, agricultural land, water bodies and settlement. It can be seen from the Table 1 that maximum area is under the agricultural land i.e. 503.15sq.km (55.43 percent) of the watershed followed by wasteland 350.40 sq.km (38.60 per-cent) out of total watershed area water bodies cover 11.95 sq.km (1.32 per-cent), forest covers 38.78 sq.km (4.27 per-cent) and settlement covers 3.45 sq.km (0.38 Per-cent).

Agricultural Land:

The land under agriculture crop is 503.15 sq.km with 55.43 percents, primarily used for farming and for production of food and cash crops Table-1 Land Use and Land Cover in 2023 food grains. It comprises land under crop (irrigated and unirrigated) fallow, plantations etc. Most

of the cropland is Kharif which includes standing crops during June to September months. It coincides with the southwest monsoon season. Rabi crops are in scattered pattern. The available agricultural land in the watershed is used for raising different crops, mainly, sorghum, cotton, soybean, pulses and vegetables. The area is low lying and marshy due to the tributaries of PurnaRiver passing through the area. Cotton, sorghum and vegetables are grown in this land. Since the land is conveniently located there is an increasing demand for urban development.

Settlements:

The supervised classification shows that there is a positive increase in the built up area under villages in Jintur. In the watershed area 152 villages are settled and covers an area of 3.45 sq.km (0.38 per-cent). The total area under built up was noticed as 3.45sq. Km in year 2023. Commercial as well as educational factors were dominating forces behind the growth of the Jintur city. The residential areas or built-up area has almost filled up at the centre of the Jintur city. Working industries are also seen in the residential areas of Jintur.

Water Bodies:

The total area covered by water bodies is 11.95 Sq.km (1.32 per cent). The class comprises areas of surface water either impounded in the form of lake and reservoirs or flowing streams, river, canals etc. There are few major streams flowing in study area which are KaidhauRiver, DudhanaRiver and KarparaRiver. These are clearly seen on satellite false colour composition imagery in blue colour. They serve as drainage courses where sewage and other wastewater of the city are led. Other water bodies of the watershed Niwali dam and Yeldari reservoir. Most of the tank water bodies are used for the purpose of drinking water for animals, washing purposes and agricultural uses. During the rainy season the tanks are almost filled with water and supply water for agriculture and to the Jintur city sufficiently.

Waste Land:

The total area covered by waste land is 350.40 sq.km is (38.60 percents). Waste lands are described as, degraded lands which can be brought under vegetative cover or under built up area. Waste land was found in northern part, eastern part and in an elongated belt running north – south in the western part of the watershed.

Forest:

A forest is a natural, self-sustaining community characterized by vertical structure created by presence of trees. The total area covered by forest is 38.78 sq.km is (4.27 per-cents). These forests are present in North-East side of Jintur watershed. Trees are large, generally single-stemmed, woody plants. Forest can exist in many different regions under a wide range of conditions, because a forest is a natural community, no forest is static in time. A forest is a biotic community predominantly of trees, shrubs and other woody vegetation, usually

with a closed canopy. This invaluable renewable natural resource is beneficial to man in many ways.

Fig.4.35 Land Use and Land Cover

Table 4.12 Land use land cover of Jintur sub- watershed

Sr No.	Class	Area in sq.km	Per cent
1	Forest	38.78	4.27
2	Agriculture (Crop)	503.15	55.43
3	Water bodies	11.95	1.32
4	Wasteland	350.40	38.60
5	Settlements	3.45	0.38
	Total	907.73	100.00

Conclusion

The Jintur watershed underwent classification based on major land use/land cover types. Utilizing Landsat 8 satellite data and Geographical Information System (GIS) techniques, distinct land use categories including Built-up lands, Agricultural lands, Forest lands, Water bodies, Barren lands, and Fallow land were identified. Analysis of Land sat 8 satellite images was employed to study the patterns of land use and land cover. Through Geographic Information System tools, diverse land use and land cover zones were mapped, providing valuable information for decision-makers in the planning process. The Jintur watershed has been categorized based on its major land use and land cover types, which include Built-up lands, Agricultural lands, Water bodies, Barren lands, and Fallow land.

References

- Alexander L. Alexandrovskiy., (2007). Rate of soil forming processes in three main model of paedogenesis. Ravista Mexicana de Ciencias Geologicas, v.24, num. 2, 2007, p. 283-292.
- Anderson J. R., Hardy E., Roach J. T. and Witmer R. E., 1983. A land use and cover classification system for use with remote sensor data. Geology Survey Professional Paper 671, p. 16.
- Baker M. E., Weller D. E., and Jordan T. E., 2006. Comparison of automated watershed delineation: Effect on land cover areas, percentage, and relationship to nutrient discharge. Photogrammetric Engineering & Remote Sensing Vol. 72, No. 2, 159-168.
- Butt A., Aziz N., 2015. Land use change mapping and analysis using remote sensing and GIS: A case study of Simply watershed, Islamabad, Pakistan. The Egyptian Journal of Remote Sensing and Space Science. Volume 18, Pages 251-259.
- Bose P., Mohapatra S. N., and Pani P., 2009. Watershed delineation and flow accumulation calculation using shuttle radar topographic mission (SRTM) data. Journal of Environmental Research and Development Vol. 4 No. 2.

- Chitra C., Alaguraja P., Ganeshkumari K., Yuvraj D., Manivel M., (2011). Watershed characteristics of Kundah sub-basin using remote sensing GIS techniques. International Journal of Geomatics and Geosciences, Vol. 2 (1), pp. 311.
- Dimyati A. (1995) Analysis of land use /land cover changes using the combination of MSS LANDSAT and land use map: case study of Yogyakarta, Indonesia. International Journal of Remote Sensing, Vol. 17, pp. 931-944.
- Doke A. B. (2017). Land use and land cover mapping of Konkan region, Maharashtra. International Journal of Current Research, Vol. 9, Issue 10, May 2017. ISSN 2231-2196.
- Giridhar M. V. S. S., Anirudh R., Rao G. S., Sowmya P., 2015. DEM processing for watershed delineation using QSWAT. International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research, vol. 6, ISSN 2229-5518.
- Horton RE., 1932. Drainage basin Characteristics. Trans Am Geophysics Union 13:350 – 361.
- Jadhav S. I., Babar Md., 2013. Morphometric analysis with reference to hydrogeological repercussion on Domri river sub-basin of Sindphana river basin, Maharashtra, India. Journal of Geosciences and Geomatics, Vol. I No. 1.
- Jawale B. V., and Bowlekar A. P., 2020. Remote sensing and GIS based approach for morphometric analysis of selected watershed in Chiplun Tehsil of Maharashtra, India. International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Science, ISSN: 2319-7706, Vol. 9.
- Karwariya S. & Goyal S., (2011). Land use and land cover mapping using digital classification technique in Tikamgarh district, Madhya Pradesh, India using remote sensing. International Journal of Geomatics and Geoscience, Volume 2, No. 2, ISSN 0976-4380
- Kaviya B., Kumar O., Verma R. C., Singh R. P., 2017. Watershed delineation using GIS in Selaiyur area. International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Volume 116 No. 13, 417-423.